

PLANNING TOOL – ENERGY COMMUNITIES

Creation of holistic concepts for decentralised renewable energy
solutions – fast and technology-neutral

HOW CAN I BENEFIT FROM USING THE TOOL?

The planning tool for energy communities provides individual and holistic solutions for municipalities, companies and emerging energy communities and allows:

Optimised integration of renewable energy

Reduced energy costs

Mitigation of CO₂ emissions

Increased energy independence

Fast and fact-based investment decision

WHAT INFORMATION DO I NEED FOR A HOLISTIC ENERGY CONCEPT?

- ✓ Current energy demand for electricity, heating, cooling (ideally load profiles)
- ✓ Data on the existing energy system and available technologies (PV, storage, heating system, ...)
- ✓ Other framework conditions such as e.g.
 - areas available for PV
 - planned participants and metering points in the case of energy communities
 - integration of e-mobility (yes/no)

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Arrange a first consultation appointment with the NEFI team!

Step 1: Collection of energy-related data and framework conditions

Step 2: Data analysis and creation of the energy concept based on mathematical optimisation calculations. In this way, it can be ensured that the optimal system is found from both an economic and ecological point of view.

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